

Northern Ireland Good Friday Agreement

Date Signed: 10 April, 1998

Accord Type: Comprehensive Peace Agreement

Country: United Kingdom

95.24

Implementation Score after 10 years

[Download full accord PDF](#)

[See the implementation visualization](#)

PROVISIONS IN THIS ACCORD

Cease Fire
Powersharing Transitional Government
Constitutional Reform
Inter-ethnic/State Relations
Electoral/Political Party Reform
Decentralization/Federalism
Dispute Resolution Committee
Judiciary Reform
Police Reform
Demobilization
Disarmament
Reintegration
Prisoner Release
Paramilitary Groups
Human Rights
Right of Self-Determination
Citizenship Reform
Women's Rights
Education Reform
Official Language and Symbol
Minority Rights
Reparations
Economic and Social Development
Ratification Mechanism
Detailed Implementation Timeline
Independence Referendum
Review of Agreement
Verification/Monitoring Mechanism

Judiciary Reform

Implementation Timeline

About this Provision

1998

Minimum Implementation

As provided for in the Good Friday Agreement and the Terms of Reference in Annex B, the review group, comprised of four civil servants representing the Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, the Lord Chancellor, the Attorney General, and five independent assessors, was formed. The review group had its first meeting on 1 July 1998 and published a consultation paper on 27 August 1998, distributing copies of this paper to political parties, individual politicians, churches, the judiciary, and a range of voluntary and community organizations with an interest in this issue. The group reviewed the criminal justice system over the past 30 years in Northern Ireland, reviewed recent changes in the legislations, and visited the Republic of Ireland, Belgium, Canada, the Netherlands, Scotland, South Africa, New Zealand, and the US to examine how other jurisdictions deliver criminal justice.¹

1. "The Good Friday Agreement: Criminal Justice Review," *BBC News*, May 2006, accessed January 29, 2013, <http://www.bbc.co.uk/northernireland/schools/agreement/policing/criminal...> "Criminal Justice System Review Report," *CAIN Web Service*, March 30, 2000, accessed January 29, 2013, <http://cain.ulst.ac.uk/issues/law/cjr/report30300.htm>.

1999

Minimum Implementation

The review group published a progress report in April 1999. After the progress report, the group held a series of nine seminars across Northern Ireland between May and June 1999 in which more than 3,000 individuals, groups, and organizations were invited for their feedback.

2000

Minimum Implementation

The review group published a report on 30 March 2000. In its 447-page review of the criminal justice system in Northern Ireland, the group made 294 recommendations on issues related to human rights, prosecution, courts, the judiciary, victims and witness, and law reform, among others. These recommendations were also related to the establishment of an independent commission to oversee the appointment of judges, the integration of restorative justice into the judicial system, and the devolution of the criminal justice system to the Northern Ireland Assembly.²

2. "Criminal Justice System Review Report."

2001

Minimum Implementation

The government was slow to respond to the review group's report. Therefore, the nationalists and the republicans called for an immediate implementation of the report. This created pressure and on 12 November 2001, the government published its implementation plan for the criminal justice review and a draft justice bill. The proposed justice draft bill, however, did not materialize between 2001 and 2008.

2002

Minimum Implementation

No developments observed this year.

2003

Minimum Implementation

No developments observed this year.

2004

Minimum Implementation

No developments observed this year.

2005

Minimum Implementation

No developments observed this year.

2006

Minimum Implementation

No developments observed this year.

2007

Minimum Implementation

No developments observed this year.

Almost a decade after the signing the Belfast Agreement (i.e., the Good Friday Agreement) and constant insistence from Sinn Fein on the unconditional transfer of police and judicial powers to Northern Ireland, on 4 February 2010, the hardliner Democratic Unionist Party (DUP) and Sinn Fein voted to approve a deal that paved the way for the transfer of judicial and policing powers.³ The deal would allow the Northern Ireland Judicial Appointment Commission (NIJAC) to select and appoint, or recommend for appointment, applicants for all listed judicial offices, up to and including High Court Judge.

3. "Northern Ireland," *Keesing's Record of World Events*, 56 (March 2010): 49754.

Please always cite: ["Annualized implementation data on comprehensive intrastate peace accords, 1989–2012."](#) Madhav Joshi, Jason Michael Quinn, and Patrick M. Regan. *Journal of Peace Research* 52 (2015): 551-562.

